

Sbrodova Kateryna, a first (bachelor's) level higher education student, 2nd year of the Faculty of Management, Accounting and Information Technologies, Odessa National Economic University, specialty D3 "Management"

Kovalskyi Andrii, PhD in Economics, Senior Lecturer at the Department of Management of Organizations, Odessa National Economic University

STAKEHOLDER INTERACTION MANAGEMENT IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF AGROVOLTAIC PROJECTS IN UKRAINE

The modern development of the agricultural sector and energy is characterized by an active search for innovative solutions that allow to increase the efficiency of the use of natural resources and ensure sustainable economic development. In this aspect, technologies that combine the production of agricultural products with the generation of renewable energy are becoming increasingly important. One of such areas is agrovoltatics, which involves the simultaneous use of land resources for growing crops and generating electricity using solar photovoltaic installations [1]. Given the growing demand for alternative energy sources and the need to increase Ukraine's energy independence, the development of agrovoltatic technologies and the implementation of various projects for their use and improvement has significant potential. In addition, the implementation of such programs requires effective interaction between different groups of stakeholders, since it is the coordination of their interests and the pooling of resources that determines the possibility of achieving the relevant goals. That is why the issue of managing stakeholder interaction in the process of implementing agrovoltatic projects is becoming extremely relevant.

The purpose of the study is to substantiating the features of managing stakeholder interaction during the implementation of agrovoltatic projects in Ukraine and identifying key management factors for increasing the efficiency of their implementation.

Agrovoltatics is a technology that involves the integration of photovoltaic systems into agricultural land for the purpose of simultaneous production of electricity and agricultural products. Such a technique allows to increase the efficiency of land resource use and creates opportunities for diversification of agricultural enterprises' incomes [2].

One of the key advantages of agrovoltatic systems is the possibility of obtaining a double economic effect. Enterprises can simultaneously receive income from the production of agricultural products and electricity generation. As a result of combining these two types of activities, the efficiency of land use can increase significantly. According to some estimates, the integrated use of land resources within agrovoltatic projects can increase the efficiency of land use up to 160% [3].

It is worth emphasizing that agrovoltaic systems can positively affect the conditions for growing crops. Solar panels create partial shading, which helps to lower soil temperature and reduce moisture evaporation. This allows you to conserve water resources and reduce the need for irrigation, which is especially important in conditions of climate change [2].

It should also be noted that the application of agrovoltaic technologies is never without certain economic challenges. Studies show that the initial investment in the creation of agrovoltaic installations can be higher compared to conventional solar power plants. For example, the cost of installing agrovoltaic systems can be about 1.3 million euros per megawatt of capacity, while traditional photovoltaic installations cost about 1 million euros per megawatt [4]. Despite the high initial costs, in the long term agrovoltaic systems can provide significant economic benefits. For example, the combination of agrovoltaics with the cultivation of horticultural crops can demonstrate significant economic potential, and calculations show the possibility of obtaining significant net present value over the long period of operation of such systems [4].

Social acceptance and collaboration with local stakeholders are critical to the successful implementation of agrovoltaic projects. For example, farmers may be reluctant to adopt these technologies without clear financial incentives or technical support. Torma and Aschemann-Witzel (2023–2024) examined perceptions, barriers, and drivers of agrovoltaic use and found that negative aspects included perceived high costs and complexity of implementation, while positive aspects included the potential to resolve land use conflicts for food and energy. Policy interventions aimed at addressing these issues, such as training programs, simplified permit procedures, and community engagement initiatives, have proven effective in increasing the adoption and sustainability of such initiatives [5].

According to scientific data from the field of renewable energy, involving stakeholders at the early stages of planning helps to increase the level of support for energy projects and reduce the risk of conflicts during their development. The participation of local communities, farmers, energy companies and authorities in the decision-making process allows to take into account the specifics of a particular territory, and also increases the level of trust in the initiators. Thanks to this approach, long-term cooperation between project participants is formed and the effectiveness of its implementation increases [6].

As agrovoltaic researchers emphasize, different stakeholder groups perceive the same characteristics differently, so interaction management should consider three levels of social acceptance: micro (market acceptance by individual players), meso (perception by the local community, e.g. visual impact on the landscape), and macro (social and political approval). Such a differentiated approach allows for the alignment of interests of almost all stakeholders, which also helps ensure the effective implementation of agrovoltaic projects [5].

In Ukraine, agrovoltaics is just beginning to take shape as a separate direction of renewable energy development. Despite the significant potential of this technology, its implementation is constrained by a number of factors, among which the lack of a clear regulatory framework for the use of agricultural land for the placement of solar power plants is an important one [1]. However, the first practical attempts to adapt

agrovoltatics to Ukrainian conditions are already appearing. For example, within the framework of the project “Territorial analysis of sustainable agricultural practices and possible integrated water-energy-food-ecosystem solutions in Ukraine”, which was implemented with the support of the French non-governmental organization “Electricities without Borders” and the French government, experts conducted consultations with farmers, representatives of cooperatives and owners of personal farms in Transcarpathia. Field visits were carried out, the state of water resources and hydraulic structures was assessed, and potential sites for pilot plants were identified. Such initiatives make it possible to combine the development of renewable energy with support for small agricultural producers and rural areas [7].

Thus, the analysis conducted allows us to state that the effectiveness of the implementation of agrovoltatic projects in Ukraine is largely determined by the quality of stakeholder interaction management. It has been established that the key factors in increasing the effectiveness of such projects are the consistency of interests of stakeholders, the timeliness of their involvement in the planning process and ensuring an appropriate level of information interaction between participants. It is substantiated that the formation of transparent cooperation mechanisms contributes to strengthening trust and increasing the effectiveness of the implementation of agrovoltatic initiatives. It is proven that the further development of such projects in Ukraine requires improving regulatory and legal regulation, developing information and consulting support and creating favorable conditions for attracting investments.

References

1. Ukrainian Agrovoltatic Association. Official website [Electronic resource]. – Available at: <https://agrivoltaic.org.ua/> (accessed: 15.03.2026).
2. Agrovoltatics in Ukraine: how to get harvest and energy from one land [Electronic resource] // Sanlarix. – Available at: <https://sanlarix.com.ua/agrovoltayika-v-ukrayini/> (accessed: 15.03.2026).
3. European experience of agrovoltatics: what Ukraine should adopt [Electronic resource] // Association of Agrovoltatics of Ukraine. – Available at: <https://agrivoltaic.org.ua/post-1233-agrivoltaicua/> (accessed: 16.03.2026).
4. Pekk L. Future of agrivoltaic projects: a review from the technological forecasting perspective [Electronic resource]. – Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666790825001806> (accessed: 16.03.2026).
5. Torma G., Aschemann-Witzel J. Social acceptance of dual land use approaches: stakeholders' perceptions of the drivers and barriers confronting agrivoltatics diffusion // *Journal of Rural Studies*. - 2023. - Vol. 97. – P. 610–625. – Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0743016723000141> (accessed: 03/22/2026).
6. Stanitsas M., Trivellas P., Mavromati A. Navigating the nexus: stakeholder engagement in hybrid renewable energy power purchase agreements (PPAs) for sustainable development // *Sustainability*. - 2024. - Vol. 16, No. 17. – Art. 7381. – Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/16/17/7381> (accessed: 03/22/2026).

7. Project continues: agrivoltaics for energy and water supply of small farms and household plots in Zakarpattia [Electronic resource] // Primavera. – Available at: <https://primavera.pp.ua/news/post/agrovoltaiacs-1> (accessed: 03/22/2026).